

Neurosteroid-based therapies for postpartum depression: mechanisms of action and clinical evidence

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Abstract

Postpartum depression (PPD) is a serious psychiatric disorder occurring during pregnancy or after childbirth that significantly affects maternal functioning, infant development, and family well-being. The pathophysiology of PPD is multifactorial and involves complex interactions between biological, psychological, and environmental factors. Increasing evidence indicates that dysregulation of neuroactive steroid signaling, particularly involving allopregnanolone and γ -aminobutyric acid type A (GABA_A) receptor modulation, may contribute to the development of depressive symptoms in the postpartum period. Neurosteroids play an essential role in regulating inhibitory neurotransmission within the central nervous system and are involved in mood stabilization, stress response, and emotional regulation. Recent advances in neuropsychopharmacology have led to the development of novel neuroactive steroid therapies targeting GABA_A receptors. Brexanolone, the first medication specifically approved for postpartum depression, and zuranolone, an orally administered synthetic neurosteroid, have demonstrated rapid antidepressant effects and promising efficacy in clinical trials. Both agents act as positive allosteric modulators of GABA_A receptors, enhancing inhibitory neurotransmission and potentially restoring impaired neurosteroid signaling associated with PPD. This review summarizes current evidence regarding the role of neurosteroids in postpartum depression and evaluates emerging neuroactive steroid therapies.

Keywords: postpartum depression, mood disorder, brexanolone, zuranolone, emerging therapies, neurosteroids

1. INTRODUCTION

Postpartum depression (PPD) is a severe psychiatric disorder affecting women during pregnancy and the postpartum period, significantly impairing maternal functioning and child well-being. Although the pathophysiology of PPD remains incompletely understood, current evidence suggests a multifactorial etiology involving biological, psychological, and environmental factors. In particular, dysregulation of neuroactive steroid signaling and altered γ -aminobutyric acid type A (GABA_A) receptor modulation have emerged as important mechanisms associated with the development of depressive symptoms after childbirth. Neurosteroids such as allopregnanolone play a critical role in the regulation of inhibitory neurotransmission within the central nervous system and may contribute to mood stabilization during pregnancy and the postpartum period. Recent advances in neuropsychopharmacology have led to the development of novel neuroactive steroid therapies targeting GABA_A receptors. Brexanolone, the first medication specifically approved for postpartum depression, and zuranolone, an orally administered synthetic neurosteroid, have demonstrated rapid antidepressant effects and favorable efficacy in clinical trials. Both agents act as positive allosteric modulators of GABA_A receptors, enhancing inhibitory neurotransmission and potentially restoring disrupted neurosteroid signaling observed in women with PPD.

This article reviews the current understanding of postpartum depression with particular emphasis on the neurobiological role of neurosteroids and GABA_A receptor modulation. Additionally, it discusses the pharmacological properties, mechanisms of action, clinical efficacy, and safety profiles of brexanolone and zuranolone as emerging therapeutic options for postpartum depression.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

A literature review was conducted using PubMed and Google Scholar databases between January 2020 and May 2025. The search strategy included the following keywords: “postpartum depression”, “brexanolone”, “zuranolone”, “neurosteroids”, “GABA_A receptor”, and “pharmacologic therapy”. Only peer-reviewed articles published in English were included. Clinical trials, systematic reviews, meta-analyses,

and relevant observational studies evaluating neuroactive steroid therapies in postpartum depression were selected. Articles unrelated to postpartum depression or lacking full-text availability were excluded.

3. CURRENT STATE OF KNOWLEDGE

A. Postpartum depression

Postpartum depression is a potentially life-threatening psychiatric disorder defined as an episode of depression occurring during pregnancy or within 4 weeks, as defined in the *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Health Disorders* (DMS-5) [1]. According to the *International Classification of Diseases 11th Revision* (ICD-11), postpartum depression is classified as a mental or behavioural disorder associated with the puerperium, with onset typically occurring within approximately 6 weeks after delivery [2]. Criteria include a combination of depressed mood, loss of interest, anhedonia, sleep and appetite disturbance, impaired concentration, psychomotor disturbance, fatigue, feelings of guilt or worthlessness, and suicidal thoughts for most of 2 weeks, clinical impairment and elimination of alternative causes. For some women those symptoms are believed to be a passing phenomenon, not requiring medical intervention. It is true for a case of postpartum blues, occurring within the first ten days of delivery, characterized by mild mood disturbance [3]. However, postpartum depression (PPD) is a clinical disorder that significantly impairs functioning and frequently necessitates professional care.

Although the estimates differ according to the period of follow-up after delivery, between 3% and 6% of women will experience the onset of a major depressive episode during pregnancy or in the weeks or months following delivery [1]. Depending on the diagnostic criteria used, the frequency of occurrence of PPD varies from 10% to 15% to as high as 30% [4, 5]. Although the overall prevalence of depression does not appear to be higher in women after delivery as compared to age-matched comparison women, serious depression requiring admission to hospital is clearly more prevalent [5, 6].

The exact pathophysiology of postpartum depression remains unclear and continues to be an important subject of ongoing research. It appears to be affected by both biologic and environmental factors. The factors identified spanned sociodemographic, biological, psychological, and obstetric domains. Among the most frequently mentioned are previous history of depression, other mental disorders, especially bipolar disorder or schizophrenia, depression or anxiety during pregnancy, positive family history of any psychiatric illness, additional life events and psychological factors such as neuroticism [6,7].

Given its relatively high prevalence and the significant risks it poses to both the mother and the child, early detection and prompt treatment are of great importance. Therefore, treatment should be individualized and include both nonpharmacologic and pharmacologic approaches.

Historically tricyclic antidepressants have been used as the first line of pharmacological treatment, later followed by the introduction of selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors (SSRIs) which offered better adverse effect profiles and tolerance, while maintaining efficacy. Although available literature supports the use of antidepressants their principal limitation remains the delayed onset of therapeutic effects, usually observed between 2 to 4 weeks after treatment initiation. In contrast to these limitations a new class of neurosteroid therapies has emerged. In recent years The U.S. Food and Drug Administration approved Brexanolone (Zulresso) and Zuranolone (Zurzuvae) to treat postpartum depression in adults. Due to their rapid onset of action and favorable efficacy profile, these therapies are emerging as promising treatment options for postpartum depression. This article aims to discuss newly proposed therapies.

B. Neurosteroids

Neurosteroids are a class of endogenous steroid molecules synthesized in the central and peripheral nervous system that modulate neuronal excitability and synaptic transmission. Peripherally synthesized

steroids can cross the blood-brain barrier and regulate gene expression that persists long after the disappearance of the steroid from the brain [8] leading to changes in mood, behavior, stress responses, cognitive functions, and sleep, and they also contribute to neuroprotection and synaptic plasticity [8]. However, some steroids can induce rapid changes in neuronal excitability within seconds, suggesting mechanisms of action that are independent of genomic pathways [9]. Traditionally, steroids were considered to function solely as hormones produced by peripheral endocrine glands, including the ovaries and adrenal glands, and therefore had to cross the blood-brain barrier to affect neuronal signaling. However, accumulating evidence indicates that the brain itself is capable of steroid synthesis [10,11]. Both neurons and glial cells in the central nervous system express the enzymatic machinery necessary for the local production of pregnane neurosteroids, either *de novo* or from circulating precursors. Consequently, these compounds may act not only as endocrine signals originating from peripheral tissues but also as locally acting paracrine modulators that regulate neuronal activity by fine-tuning the function of the GABA_A receptor. Neurosteroids interact with the GABA_A receptor as stereoselective positive allosteric modulators. Through binding to specific allosteric sites, they potentiate GABAergic signaling by increasing the probability and duration of the open state of the GABA-gated chloride channel [8]. At higher concentrations (≥ 100 nM), neurosteroids are capable of directly activating the GABA_A receptor-channel complex, producing a GABA-mimetic effect [8, 10]. In this case, the steroids no longer act solely as positive allosteric modulators but can directly open the receptor-associated chloride channel, leading to enhanced inhibitory signaling and suppression of excitatory neurotransmission [8]. In addition to inducing anaesthesia, lower doses of steroids produced anxiolytic, analgesic, anticonvulsant, sedative and hypnotic effects [8].

c. Brexanolone

Reproductive hormones regulate biological pathways associated with the development of major depression. They also influence emotional regulation, cognitive functioning, arousal, and motivation, which means they may indirectly contribute to postpartum depression by affecting psychological and social risk factors. Research suggests that estradiol influences several neurobiological mechanisms associated with mood regulation and depression [12]. One of the main hypotheses proposed in the literature is that postpartum depression may not result from abnormal hormone concentrations per se, but rather from an increased sensitivity of certain women to the rapid hormonal fluctuations occurring after childbirth. In particular, the abrupt decline in estrogen and progesterone levels during the postpartum period may trigger affective dysregulation in biologically susceptible individuals [12]. It affects factors related to neuronal growth, plasticity, and cellular signaling in ways that resemble the action of antidepressant medications [13]. Progesterone plays an important role in the regulation of several biological pathways linked to emotional functioning and stress regulation [14]. Disturbances in these mechanisms have been associated with the pathophysiology of depression. Changes in neuroactive steroid metabolites have also been associated with postpartum depression. One of the most important neurosteroids is allopregnanolone, an endogenous, potent positive allosteric modulator of synaptic and extrasynaptic γ -aminobutyric acid type A (GABA_A) receptors and neuroactive steroid, a progesterone metabolite that modulates GABA_A receptor activity. Previous studies have demonstrated a relationship between decreased GABA levels and more severe depressive symptoms among women vulnerable to postpartum depression [15]. Similarly, reduced concentrations of allopregnanolone during pregnancy have been associated with a higher risk of depressive symptoms, while elevated levels appear to have a protective effect against postpartum depression. [16,17]. Levels of allopregnanolone rise significantly throughout pregnancy and rapidly decline in the postpartum period, which has been hypothesized to contribute to the pathophysiology of postpartum depression. Allopregnanolone-related signaling pathways have also emerged as a potential therapeutic target, and clinical studies have shown that brexanolone may reduce depressive symptoms in women with postpartum depression. Brexanolone structurally mimics allopregnanolone, which is a natural progesterone metabolite

that is produced by the corpus luteum and placenta during pregnancy [18]. Activation of GABA_A receptors is associated with suppression of neuronal activity in the brain through inhibitory neurotransmission. The binding of GABA to GABA_A receptors results in an opening of the transmembrane channel, and the influx of chloride results in suppression of neural activity in the brain [19]. Brexanolone administration enhances the inhibitory effects induced by GABA binding to GABA_A receptors, resulting in enhanced inhibitory signaling within the central nervous system. This modulation of GABAergic pathways is believed to reduce anxiety levels and alleviate depressive symptoms in women with postpartum depression [19]. Through restoration of neurosteroid-mediated GABAergic signaling, brexanolone may reduce depressive symptoms in affected women.

A review of 26 studies identified six comparable analyses assessing brexanolone and SSRIs using HAM-D scores. Matching-adjusted indirect comparisons showed that brexanolone produced greater reductions in depressive symptoms in women with postpartum depression, particularly during the early stages of treatment. Differences between brexanolone and SSRIs decreased over time, but overall findings support the effectiveness of brexanolone in postpartum depression [20,21].

Brexanolone demonstrates linear and dose-dependent pharmacokinetics, with extensive tissue distribution, high plasma protein binding, and relatively rapid elimination from the body. Unlike many other medications, it is metabolized primarily through non-cytochrome P450 pathways, which reduces the likelihood of significant drug–drug interactions. Studies have shown that its pharmacokinetic profile is generally not substantially altered in patients with hepatic or renal impairment, although its use is not recommended in end-stage renal disease due to the risk of accumulation of excipients used in the intravenous formulation [22]. Brexanolone is eliminated through both fecal and urinary excretion. Pharmacodynamically, brexanolone acts by enhancing GABAergic neurotransmission through positive modulation of GABA_A receptors, thereby increasing inhibitory signaling in the central nervous system [23, 24]. This mechanism is believed to contribute to its therapeutic effects in postpartum depression. Sedation has been identified as one of the main dose-related adverse effects, particularly when brexanolone is used concomitantly with other central nervous system depressants such as benzodiazepines or antidepressants. Current evidence also suggests that brexanolone does not significantly affect cardiac electrophysiology, including QT interval prolongation [23]. Brexanolone was administered as a continuous 60-hour intravenous infusion in a certified healthcare setting and was available commercially only through a restricted program (ZULRESSO® Risk Evaluation and Mitigation Strategy; REMS) due to the risk of excessive sedation or sudden loss of consciousness during administration. [25].

Recently, brexanolone has been discontinued by the manufacturer. It was the first drug specifically approved for the treatment of postpartum depression and the first neuroactive steroid used for this indication. However, it is no longer produced and is currently not recommended in clinical practice.

D. Zuranolone

Zuranolone is a novel, synthetic, neuroactive steroid GABA_A receptor positive allosteric modulator designed with the pharmacokinetic properties to support oral daily dosing. It is selective for this receptor only. It affects nine unique human recombinant subtypes in total [26].

It also acts synergistically with diazepam in a non-competitive way. To evaluate the interaction between diazepam and zuranolone, an isobolographic analysis based on the method described by Tallarida was performed. The analysis compared the concentrations required to achieve a defined pharmacological effect when the drugs were administered separately and in combination. The results demonstrated a synergistic interaction, indicating that lower doses of both compounds were sufficient to produce the same therapeutic effect when used together. Such an approach may help reduce the risk of adverse effects associated with higher-dose monotherapy [26].

Zuranolone was found to enhance HAMD-17 scores and alleviate depression symptoms in women with PPD by day 15, compared to a placebo [27]. These effects were noticeable from day 3 and persisted up to 45 days [27]. Additionally, patients reported better anxiety, global, and maternal functioning. In MDD patients, a 14-day zuranolone treatment reduced depressive symptoms as per the HAM-D score. In a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled study conducted in 543 individuals with major depressive disorder, treatment with zuranolone 50 mg once daily for 14 days resulted in a significant reduction in depressive symptoms compared with placebo [28]. Clinical improvement was observed early during therapy, highlighting the rapid onset of action of the drug. Zuranolone was also found to be generally safe and well tolerated, supporting its potential utility as a novel antidepressant treatment [29, 30].

The safety profile of zuranolone appears to be generally favorable; however, several adverse effects have been consistently reported across clinical trials and post-marketing documentation. The most frequently observed treatment-emergent adverse events include somnolence, dizziness, sedation, headache, nausea, diarrhea, and fatigue [31]. In phase III studies evaluating zuranolone in women with postpartum depression, somnolence and sedation were among the most common adverse reactions, occurring in more than 10% of participants receiving active treatment. Most adverse events were classified as mild to moderate in severity and rarely led to treatment discontinuation. Importantly, no clinically significant abnormalities in laboratory parameters, electrocardiographic findings, or vital signs were observed during the trials. Nevertheless, the sedative properties of zuranolone raise important safety considerations, particularly regarding impairment of psychomotor performance and driving ability. Consequently, the U.S. Food and Drug Administration included a boxed warning recommending that patients avoid driving or engaging in hazardous activities for at least 12 hours after each dose [31]. Additionally, concomitant use with central nervous system depressants or alcohol may potentiate sedation and cognitive impairment. Although current evidence suggests good short-term tolerability, the limited duration of follow-up and the lack of extensive long-term safety data indicate the need for further research evaluating prolonged exposure and repeated treatment courses.

In 2023, the FDA approved zuranolone (Zurzuvae) for the treatment of postpartum psychiatric disorders (PPDs), followed by approval from the European Medicines Agency (EMA) in 2025.

4. DISCUSSION

Postpartum depression remains a major public health concern due to its negative consequences for maternal mental health, infant development, and family functioning. Although selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors remain the standard pharmacological treatment, their delayed onset of action may limit their usefulness in acute postpartum conditions, particularly in women experiencing severe depressive symptoms or suicidal ideation. In this context, neuroactive steroid therapies such as brexanolone and zuranolone represent a significant advancement in the treatment of postpartum depression by targeting GABAergic neurotransmission and neurosteroid dysregulation.

One of the major clinical advantages of brexanolone and zuranolone is their rapid onset of antidepressant action, with symptom improvement observed within days of treatment initiation. Rapid reduction of depressive symptoms may be particularly important during the postpartum period, as it can improve maternal functioning, facilitate mother-infant bonding, and reduce the negative impact of maternal depression on early child development. Early symptom control may also decrease the risk of chronic depressive episodes and improve overall quality of life in affected women.

Despite these promising therapeutic effects, several important limitations should be considered. Brexanolone requires continuous 60-hour intravenous administration in a certified healthcare setting and mandatory monitoring under REMS program due to the risk of excessive sedation and sudden loss of consciousness during treatment. Additionally, the high cost of therapy and limited accessibility may significantly restrict its widespread clinical implementation. Although zuranolone offers the advantage of

oral administration, commonly reported adverse effects include somnolence, dizziness, sedation, and impaired psychomotor performance.

Another important limitation of currently available studies is the relatively short duration of follow-up. Most clinical trials evaluating brexanolone and zuranolone assessed outcomes over several weeks, making the long-term efficacy, safety, and relapse prevention potential of these therapies uncertain. In addition, many studies included relatively small patient populations, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to broader clinical practice.

Future research should focus on long-term treatment outcomes, comparative effectiveness with standard antidepressants, and the identification of biomarkers that may predict therapeutic response to neuroactive steroid treatment. Moreover, heterogeneity in study design, patient populations, and outcome assessment methods may complicate direct comparison between available clinical trials. Improved understanding of individual biological susceptibility to postpartum depression may support the development of more personalized therapeutic strategies. Further investigation into neurosteroid signaling pathways may also contribute to the discovery of novel therapeutic targets for mood disorders beyond postpartum depression.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Postpartum depression is a multifactorial disorder associated with significant consequences for maternal and infant health. Dysregulation of neurosteroid signaling and GABA_A receptor function appears to contribute to its development. Brexanolone and zuranolone have introduced a new therapeutic approach characterized by rapid antidepressant effects and promising clinical efficacy. Despite encouraging results, additional studies are needed to evaluate their long-term safety and clinical applicability.

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